

RRI2SCALE Indicators Database

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RRI2SCALE

RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH & INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS AT REGIONAL SCALE

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PROJECT INFORMATION

TITLE	RRI2SCALE – Responsible Research and Innovation Ecosystems at Regional Scale for Intelligent Cities, Transport and Energy
START DATE	1 January 2020
DURATION	36 months
WEBSITE	https://rri2scale.eu/
COORDINATOR	AGENZIA PER LA PROMOZIONE DELLA RICERCA EUROPEA - Italy
PROJECT OVERVIEW	RRI2SCALE has designed a robust methodological approach to assist regional R&I governance systems to effectively and sustainably address their Regional Dilemmas. Techno-moral scenarios will be “tested” via JRC’s Scenario Exploration System and Regional Dialogues, forming the basis for elaborating Regional Agendas and Roadmaps towards the integration of RRI principles into territorial R&I design. All project results will form the RRI2SCALE Toolkit for replication by other territories.
CONSORTIUM	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. AGENZIA PER LA PROMOZIONE DELLA RICERCA EUROPEA https://www.apre.it/ 2. HOGSKULEN PA VESTLANDET https://www.hvl.no/ 3. UNIVERSITEIT MAASTRICHT https://www.maastrichtuniversity.nl/ 4. UNIVERSITEIT TWENTE https://www.utwente.nl/en/ 5. Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC https://qplan-intl.gr/ 6. RESEARCH AND INNOVATION MANAGEMENT GMBH https://www.research-and-innovation-management.com/ 7. WHITE RESEARCH SPRL https://white-research.eu/ 8. HORDALAND FYLKESKOMMUNE https://www.hordaland.no/ 9. PROVINCIE OVERIJSEL https://www.overijssel.nl/ 10. KRITI https://www.crete.gov.gr/ 11. AXENCIA GALEGA DE INNOVACION http://gain.xunta.gal/

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Abbreviations

CEImG - Galician Network of Research Ethics Committees
DPA - Data Protection Authority
DPO - Data Protection Officer
eCTA - ethical Constructive Technology Assessment
EEA - European Economic Area
FAIR - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GA – Grant Agreement
GDPR - General Data Protection Regulation
GERD - Gross domestic expenditure on Research & Development
HRST - Human resources in science and technology
M - Methods
M&E - Monitoring and Evaluation
NUTS - Nomenclature of territorial units for statistics
O – Objectives
RES - Regional Energy Strategy
R&I - Research and Innovation
RRI - Responsible Research and Innovation
RTDI - Research, Technology, Development and Innovation
SDGs - Sustainable Development Goals
SES - Scenario Exploration System
TA - Technology Assessment

Executive Summary

The document at hand is part of the work done under Task 5.2, “Monitoring of regions’ progress towards addressing Regional Dilemmas”, which aimed to measure key RRI2SCALE activities’ performance and impact.

As a first step, Task 5.2 further elaborated the Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) framework developed in Task 5.1¹, specifying the indicators list for intelligent cities, transport and energy fields. About 100 indicators were drafted to measure progress towards key project objectives, such as transforming and opening up the R&I policy-making processes of the four regional authorities and making the regional R&I ecosystems more open, transparent and democratic. The updated list of indicators was configured after consulting (i) the work done in Task 5.1², (ii) the output of previous Horizon 2020 projects funded by the European Commission, such as MoRRI³, SUPER_MoRRI⁴ and TeRRIFICA⁵, (iii) the report from the Expert Group on Policy Indicators for RRI⁶, and (iv) feedback received from RRI2SCALE consortium partners. Also, the most efficient methods to collect data were selected, and the necessary material, including templates and questionnaires, a privacy notice and a data subject request form, were created. In other words, the first part of the current document presents an updated and more complete version of the RRI2SCALE M&E framework (see Section 3).

Throughout the project, regional authorities and other project partners closely monitored the updated indicators list and collected the necessary data. Three data collection methods were primarily employed: (i) Regional authorities compiled short reports based on semi-structured templates every four months; (ii) Feedback collection from participants in key project activities, such as the multistakeholder dialogues and the WP4 co-creation workshops.; and (iii) Online data collection from Eurostat (every four months). In parallel, a [reporting database](#) was created on Microsoft Teams where partners could upload the data they collected in an aggregate and anonymised form. The database included information on the data collected per region, the stakeholders involved in their collection, the timing of the collection, the issues encountered, and the outcomes obtained.

Finally, the combined efforts of the RRI2SCALE consortium led to an information-rich [database](#) with details of the project activities’ performance and impact (more than 50 replies were received from various stakeholders). As a result, the second part of the current document presents the key quantitative and qualitative findings (see Section 4). The collected data were regularly presented to all RRI2SCALE partners in dedicated bi-monthly meetings allowing them to exchange lessons learnt and discuss potential improvements to the project approach. Also, a detailed analysis of the collected data takes place in Task 5.3 to assess the RRI2SCALE outcomes, impacts and perceptions change.

The RRI2SCALE M&E framework is an all-inclusive framework that can be used by other European regions that wish to adopt the RRI2SCALE approach or, in general, for replication in future Research, Technology, Development and Innovation (RTDI) projects with similar objectives.

1. Introduction

RRI2SCALE is a three-year Horizon 2020 SwafS project (Grant Agreement No 872526) that seeks to embed RRI values in the policy-making processes of four European regions, namely Vestland (Norway), Overijssel (the Netherlands), Kriti (Greece) and Galicia (Spain).

The document at hand is **deliverable 5.2, “RRI2SCALE Indicators database”**. It presents the activities and outcomes of Task 5.2, “Monitoring of regions’ progress towards addressing Regional Dilemmas”. Task 5.2 is part of the work done under Work Package 5, “Monitoring, evaluation and assessment”, which is set to measure the performance, outcomes and impacts of the RRI2SCALE project.

The remaining document consists of the following sections:

- **Section 2** articulates the overall approach and methodology implemented. It further specifies the purpose of the RRI2SCALE monitoring, evaluation and assessment (M&E) framework, describes the activities to be monitored and presents the data collection and data management processes.
- **Section 3** elaborates on an updated list of indicators designed to measure the progress towards the RRI2SCALE project objectives.
- **Section 4** is the RRI2SCALE Indicators Database. It calculates and presents the indicator values for each pilot region and unveils interesting responses from questionnaire respondents.
- **Section 5** provides the main conclusions of Task 5.2 activities and guides the project’s next steps.

The **Annexes** of the current document include the questionnaires and forms employed to collect the necessary data. They also include the privacy policy and the subject request form shared as templates with the RRI2SCALE partners.

2. Methodology

2.1 Interrelations Between Tasks

Overall, the current document builds on the work done in Task 5.1, “Designing the RRI2SCALE monitoring, evaluation and assessment framework”, and produces useful quantitative and qualitative data to feed in the activities of T5.3, “Assessing the RRI2SCALE Outcomes, Impacts and Perceptions change”. The following figure aims to disambiguate the role and activities of each Task.

Figure 1: Interrelations between Tasks

In particular, within **Task 5.1**, UM-MERIT led the development of the RRI2SCALE M&E framework based on a literature review.⁷ In Task 5.2, that framework and its indicators were further elaborated to consider the specificities of each region and adjusted to the fields of intelligent cities, intelligent transport and intelligent energy. Then,

regional authorities and other project partners closely monitored the updated indicators list and collected the necessary data. The values of the monitored indicators were reported in the RRI2SCALE Indicators Database. Later, within **Task 5.3**, these outcomes were analysed and interpreted to uncover the project’s impact.

2.2 Overall Approach

Task 5.2 was implemented in six phases, depicted in Figure 2 and further described below.

Figure 2: Methodology for the implementation of Task 5.2

First phase. The RRI2SCALE M&E framework of Task 5.1 (developed by UM-MERIT) was further elaborated and supplemented by the appropriate monitoring methods and tools. In particular, Q-PLAN, with the contribution of the other Task 5.2 partners: (i) defined the purpose of the M&E framework and the objectives of the RRI2SCALE project as derived from the Grant Agreement’s (GA) “Expected Impact” section; (ii) identified the methods for collecting data throughout the various project activities; (iii) specified the appropriate indicators; and (iv) created the necessary tools (reports and questionnaires) to be used for data collection. At the end of the first phase, the RRI2SCALE M&E framework had been updated and populated with appropriate indicators and tools for monitoring purposes.

The RRI2SCALE M&E framework is an all-inclusive framework that can be used by other European regions that wish to adopt the RRI2SCALE approach or, in general, for replication in future Research, Technology, Development and Innovation (RTDI) projects with similar objectives.

Second phase. The RRI2SCALE M&E framework was communicated and tailored to the regional authorities’ needs, making it a valuable and meaningful tool for our project. Through four bilateral consultations, the updated indicators list was aligned with each regional authorities’ needs, concerns and capabilities for data collection and reporting. At the end of this phase, the regional authorities selected the indicator subsets appropriate to their circumstances, ensuring that they (with the assistance of their supporting partners) could provide the necessary data periodically. During this phase, coordination with related tasks of the project (Task 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, 4.1, 4.2, 5.1, 5.3) also took place, ensuring continuity across the different project activities and enhancing the ability of Task 5.2 to collect data in key moments of the project, such as the agenda co-creation workshops.

Third phase. The RRI2SCALE reporting database was developed (available on [Zenodo](#)), and the partners were trained to use it to report collected data. In particular, Q-PLAN set up a reporting database on the Microsoft Teams online environment and provided access to regional authorities and their supporting partners to enable them

periodically provide their monitoring data. In parallel, Q-PLAN trained them on using the reporting database and ensured compliance with data management provisions (described in Section 2.6). The training took place in a dedicated session in the RRI2SCALE 5th consortium meeting held on the 18th of January 2022.

Fourth phase. The necessary data was collected. A strategic approach to data collection was followed, comprising the following data collection methods:

1. Regional reports every 4 months
Regional authorities compiled short reports (i.e., Regional reports) based on semi-structured templates every four months to collect quantitative and qualitative data about any initiative they undertake to embed RRI into their governance framework.
2. Feedback collection at key moments of the project
Feedback collection from participants in key project activities, such as the multistakeholder dialogues (in Task 3.2) and the agenda co-creation workshops (in Task 4.1).
3. Online data collection from Eurostat
Online data collection from Eurostat (every four months) to find relevant and available statistical data at the sub-national (NUTS 2) level to facilitate understanding of the region's overarching trends.

Fifth phase. The data collected per indicator and region was shared (after anonymisation) with the Task 5.3 leader (UM-MERIT) to provide a continuous feed to the evaluation process. The output of this phase was the data-rich RRI2SCALE Indicators Database (available on [Zenodo](#) as "Monitoring Results"). Also, Q-PLAN organised bi-monthly meetings where any data collected was presented, and partners could reflect on the results and exchange ideas. In particular, four such meetings took place and constituted an opportunity for fertile discussions.

Sixth phase. Deliverable 5.2 was finalised. It describes the work done in Task 5.2 and includes the data collected/generated. It was reviewed by UM-MERIT and RIM and submitted on December 2022.

Throughout the entire Task 5.2, Q-PLAN ensured smooth management of activities and information flows by frequently coordinating with the WP leader (UM-MERIT), the involved regional authorities and their supporting partners, as well as related Task leaders (Task 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, 4.1, 4.2, 5.1, 5.3).

2.3 M&E Framework Purpose

The purpose of the RRI2SCALE M&E framework is to monitor how the project contributes toward addressing the four regions' (i.e., Vestland, Overijssel, Kriti and Galicia) regional dilemmas.

Regional Dilemmas are defined as challenges that regional authorities face when developing and implementing regional R&I strategies that both (i) boost innovation and economic growth in their territory and (ii) advance other social and environmental objectives. According to the GA's section 2.1, RRI2SCALE contributes toward addressing the four regions' Regional Dilemmas mainly by aiming to (i) transform and open up the R&I policy-making processes of the four regional authorities; (ii) make the regional R&I ecosystems* more open,

* When referring to a region's R&I ecosystem, the large number and diverse participants and resources necessary for innovation, including entrepreneurs, investors, researchers, university faculty, venture capitalists, business development and other technical service providers, are meant. Source: *Thomas, M. Innovation ecosystems as drivers of regional innovation - validating the ecosystem. Know Hub. Available at: <https://tinyurl.com/ykxuhk2z>*

transparent and democratic; and (iii) stimulate other positive societal, democratic, environmental, economic and scientific developments that address regional & global challenges.

Based on the above, the purpose of the RRI2SCALE M&E framework was to monitor the progress toward the following three objectives (O):

-
01. Transforming and opening up the R&I policy-making processes of the four regional authorities
 RRI2SCALE facilitated the adoption by regional authorities of R&I policy-making methods (e.g., design strategies) that look into the future and prepare policy-makers for the technological and research developments of forthcoming years. In parallel, the project promoted the embodiment of RRI practices into the R&I policy-making process to capture weak societal signals and encourage interactiveness among societal actors, collaborative decision-making and shared responsibility. Finally, emphasis was placed on making these changes sustainable beyond the project’s lifetime.
-
02. Making the regional R&I ecosystems more open, transparent and democratic
 RRI2SCALE facilitated the implementation of measures to (i) foster public engagement in all regional R&I processes; (ii) provide open access to the research outcomes; (iii) improve science literacy (e.g., through science education); (iv) promote gender equality in the regional R&I ecosystem; (v) consider ethics and social values in all R&I processes; and (vi) restructure R&I governance systems to make them more inclusive and transparent.
-
03. Stimulating positive developments towards addressing regional & global challenges
 This objective includes promoting intelligent technology solutions to foster prosperity and expediting progress towards the United Nations’ Sustainable Development Objectives (SDGs).

The above objectives and their sub-objectives are summarised in the following table.

Table 1: The project objectives and sub-objectives monitored

01	Transforming and opening up the R&I policy-making processes of the four regional authorities
i	Adopting R&I policy-making methods (e.g., design strategies) that look into the future
ii	Embodying RRI practices into the R&I policy-making process and governance framework
iii	Making changes sustainable beyond the lifetime of the project
02	Making the regional R&I ecosystems more open, transparent and democratic
i	Foster public engagement
ii	Provide open access
iii	Improving science literacy
iv	Promoting gender equality
v	Considering ethics
vi	Mainstreaming RRI in R&I governance frameworks
03	Stimulating positive developments towards addressing regional & global challenges
i	Promoting intelligent technology solutions
ii	Expediting progress towards SDGs

As defined in Deliverable 5.1, analysing data regarding the progress towards these objectives “promotes learning and improve our knowledge, so we can support attempts to enhance policy-making processes and outcomes of research and innovation in the participating regions”.

2.4 Data Collection Methods

Three primary methods were employed to collect the necessary data.

2.4.1 Method 1: Regional Reports every 4 Months

The four regional authorities were requested to complete a short report every four months starting from month 26 (i.e., February 2022). The report's purpose was not to capture the performance and outcomes of specific project activities but to monitor any additional initiatives undertaken by the regional authorities, such as institutional changes (see [Annexe 1](#)).

Our consortium opted to collect such data every four months (starting February 2022) instead of six months (as mentioned in the GA). The reason is that although WP1, WP2 and WP3 were granted a 2-month extension by the European Commission, WP5 and the project overall did not get a similar extension. Thus, some Task 5.2 activities had to be compressed in terms of timing to allow for the timely delivery of results. Also, this approach left two months spare at the end of the project to prepare D5.2 and D5.3.

2.4.2 Method 2: Feedback Collection at key Project Moments

RRI2SCALE collected data on key moments of the project. More specifically, it collected data during or after completing project activities with significant interaction with stakeholders and a high potential to contribute towards project objectives. Such activities were the following:

1. Provision of training to the personnel of the four regional authorities

In the frame of Task 3.1, RRI2SCALE held training sessions and developed training material to guide the personnel of the four regional authorities on designing and implementing participatory R&I policy-making processes. The training material included, among others, (i) guidelines for the construction of techno-moral scenarios and the use of the SES game; (ii) methods for inclusion and representation of citizens and stakeholders in policy-making processes; and (iii) formats and guidelines for facilitating the policy-making processes to warrant the deliberative quality. After the training sessions, participants were asked to fill in a feedback questionnaire (see [Annexe 2](#)).

2. Organisation of regional multi-stakeholder dialogues

In the context of Task 3.2, RRI2SCALE invited regional R&I stakeholders to experiment with the techno-moral scenarios using the SES simulation tool. The tool presented scenario situations for each focus domain (i.e., intelligent cities, intelligent transport, and intelligent energy) across multiple timelines. Thus, it helped create awareness among stakeholders and identify their specific challenges, issues, concerns, and interests in using and exploiting technologies for social benefit. After the simulation session (commonly referred to as "multistakeholder dialogues"), participants were asked to fill in a feedback questionnaire (see [Annexe 3](#)).

3. Elaboration of regional innovation agendas and roadmaps

In Task 4.1, RRI2SCALE organised two regional co-creation workshops with regional R&I stakeholders to (i) set the constituting elements of the innovation agendas and (ii) work towards transforming the agendas into roadmaps. Both documents (i) proposed concrete institutional changes in the participating regional organisations to embed RRI in their R&I processes; and (ii) spurred sustainable and measurable changes in all four regional R&I ecosystems to make them more inclusive and responsible. After the first workshop, participants were asked to fill in a feedback questionnaire (see [Annexe 4](#)).

All the above questionnaires and reports collected quantitative (Likert-scale ratio) data but also included a few open-ended questions to get descriptive answers and accommodate an extensive range of different responses from respondents.

2.4.3 *Method 3: Online Data Collection from Eurostat*

As Task 5.2 leader, Q-PLAN performed an online search on Eurostat every four months (starting from Jan 2022) to find secondary data that allow understanding of overarching trends in the region and how the developed agendas and roadmaps could contribute towards O3.

2.4.4 Overview of the M&E Framework Architecture

The following table provides the reader with an overview of the RRI2SCALE M&E framework architecture.

Table 2: Overview of the M&E Framework Architecture

#	Monitoring methods	What was monitored?	Data collection tool	Data collection frequency	Responsible for data collection	Identifier
1	Regional reports every 4 months	Institutional changes in regional authorities	Regional reports	Every four months (beginning Feb. 2022)	RRI2SCALE regional authorities	M1
2	Feedback collection at key project moments	Task 3.1 Training	Feedback Questionnaire	Once, after the training	Q-PLAN, in collaboration with Task 3.1 partners	M2.1
		Task 3.2 Multi-stakeholder dialogues	Feedback Questionnaire	Once, after the dialogue	Q-PLAN, in collaboration with Task 3.2 partners	M2.2
		Task 4.1 1 st co-creation workshop	Feedback Questionnaire	Once, after the workshop	Q-PLAN, in collaboration with Task 4.1 partners	M2.3
3	Online data collection from Eurostat	Overarching trends	Eurostat	Every four months (beginning Feb. 2022)	Q-PLAN	M3

2.5 Data Management Provisions

The RRI2SCALE consortium handles personal data with due diligence. It respects the provisions of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and takes any steps required to make the data collected/generated FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). In Task 5.2, we collected personal details, such as the stakeholder group, gender and job position. Thus, we adopted measures to comply with all the Art. 5 GDPR principles relating to the processing of personal data.⁸ The below are also in line with the RRI2SCALE Data Management Plan (Deliverable 7.2).

- **Principle 1: Lawfulness, fairness and transparency principle**
The personal data was processed lawfully, fairly, and transparently in relation to the data subject. All questionnaire respondents have provided us with consent to handle their personal data after reading the respective consent form and privacy policy (see [Annexe 5](#)). At the same time, a data subject request form was provided to them to support any future data requests (see [Annexe 6](#)).
- **Principle 2: Purpose limitation**
The personal data was collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes (e.g., to evaluate the impact of key RRI2SCALE activities) and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes.
- **Principle 3: Data minimisation**
The personal data was adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed. For example, the responsibility for contacting stakeholders and sharing with them the questionnaires was appointed to the regional authorities. In doing so, no additional personal data, such as names and emails, had to be collected centrally by the task leader, Q-PLAN.
- **Principle 4: Accuracy**
The personal data was accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date. To this end, we implemented checks to correct, update, or erase incorrect or incomplete data that came in.
- **Principle 5: Storage limitation**
We retain personal data to achieve our research purposes and comply with the applicable laws, regulations, and contractual obligations to which we are subject. For instance, we must retain some data for up to five years after the project ends. After the expiry of the retention period, and unless further legitimate grounds for retention arise, we will securely erase any personal data.
- **Principle 6: Integrity and confidentiality**
We apply a personal data risk assessment process to identify, analyse, and evaluate the security risks that may threaten personal data. Based on the risk assessment results, we define and apply a set of technical and organisational measures to mitigate security risks.

On top of the above, after completing the Task 5.2 activities, any necessary action was taken to make the data collected/generated FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). First, the data controller (Q-PLAN) undertook all the necessary anonymisation procedures to adjust the data so that the data subjects are no longer identifiable. Then, the data was uploaded to [Zenodo](#), which automatically links to OpenAIRE. Finally, data findability was fostered thanks to the metadata (description, keywords, etc) that was included.

3. Indicators List

Section 3 presents the list of indicators employed to measure the progress toward each of the RRI2SCALE objectives. The indicators are grouped according to the objective or sub-objective they relate. Also, on the right side of each table, the reader can find information on the collection method employed for each indicator.

3.1 Transforming and Opening Up the R&I Policy-Making Processes of the Four Regional Authorities (O1)

The indicators within this subsection aimed to measure progress towards O1. Thus, they incorporate feedback gathered only by regional policy-makers, regional authorities employees, and other agents involved in policy-making and implementation (including both political persons and civil servants). Hereunder, we refer to all these categories of people as “policy-makers”.

Table 3: Indicators that measure progress towards O1

Identifier	Indicator	Collection
Adopting R&I Policy-Making Methods that Look into the Future		
SP.DS.1	Number of policy-makers who reported a better understanding of the importance of informing policy-makers about estimations on future developments (e.g., technological, demographical and research developments) in their region before engaging in any R&I policy-making process / Total number of policy-makers surveyed*	M2.1
SP.DS.2	Number of policy-makers reported that their participation in the RRI2SCALE training helped them organise the multistakeholder dialogue (or the Scenario Exploration System - SES session, as commonly called) of their region / Total number of policy-makers surveyed	M2.1
SP.DS.3	Number of policy-makers reported that their participation in the SES session contributed to appreciating the positions of different stakeholders / Total number of policy-makers surveyed	M2.2
SP.DS.4	Number of policy-makers reported that their participation helped them to perceive new technologies such as intelligent cities, intelligent transport and intelligent energy as part of the solution to regional problems and dilemmas rather than the problem / Total number of policy-makers surveyed	M2.2
SP.DS.5	Number of policy-makers reported that their participation helped them to understand potential developments (e.g., technological, demographical and economic	M2.2

* To measure this indicator, survey respondents were asked the following question: “Do you believe that familiarising policy-makers with estimations about future developments (e.g., technological, demographical and research developments) in their region is crucial for their strategic planning process?” Potential answers were: (i) Very much; (ii) Somewhat; (iii) Neutral; (iv) Not really; (v) Not at all; and (vi) Undecided. The outcome of the indicator was calculated by aggregating those who replied “Very much” and “Somewhat”. The values of the remaining indicators are calculated similarly. The exact phrasing of the questions can be found in the questionnaires in Annexes.

	developments) that could affect their region by 2022 and beyond / Total number of policy-makers surveyed	
Embodying RRI Practices into the R&I Policy-Making Process and Governance Framework		
SP.EP.1	Number of policy-makers reported the RRI2SCALE training familiarised them with practices to capture weak societal signals (e.g., people's feelings) when they organise strategic planning processes / Total number of policy-makers surveyed	M2.1
SP.EP.2	Number of policy-makers reported a better understanding of the importance of promoting multi-stakeholder engagement in the region's R&I policy-making as a measure to democratise decision-making / Total number of policy-makers surveyed	M2.3
SP.EP.3	Number of policy-makers reported that they would undertake initiatives to increase public engagement in the strategic planning of their region / Total number of policy-makers surveyed	M2.3
SP.EP.4	Number of policy-makers reported a better understanding of the importance of considering ethics and social values as a measure to achieve higher acceptance of R&I-related public policies / Total number of policy-makers surveyed	M2.2
SP.EP.5	Number of policy-makers reported the RRI2SCALE training familiarised them with practices to encourage interactiveness among stakeholders when they organise strategic planning processes / Total number of policy-makers surveyed	M2.1
SP.EP.7	Number of policy-makers reported that their participation helped them to understand current dilemmas in their region better / Total number of policy-makers surveyed	M2.2
SP.EP.8	Number of policy-makers reported a better understanding of how to design and implement participatory processes / Total number of policy-makers surveyed	M2.1
Making Changes Sustainable Beyond the Lifetime of the Project		
SP. SC.2	Number of regional authorities reported that the higher-level policy-makers of their regions are aware of the RRI concept / Total number of regional authorities	M1
SP. SC.3	Number of regional authorities reported that the higher-level policy-makers consider the RRI concept as crucial for the R&I ecosystem and the prosperity of their region / Total number of regional authorities	M1
SP. SC.4	Number of regional authorities reported that the tools and methods introduced by the RRI2SCALE project, such as the training on stakeholder dialogues, the SES game, the agendas and roadmaps, have been communicated to higher-level policy-makers to consider their permanent or extended use / Total number of regional authorities	M1
SP. SC.5	Number of regional authorities reported that higher-level policy-makers consider the tools and methods introduced by the RRI2SCALE project as meaningful and plan to use them in the future / Total number of regional authorities	M1

Apart from the above indicators, the representatives were asked to reply to a set of open-ended questions that aimed to capture and regularly monitor the integration of RRI practices into regional authorities' R&I governance frameworks and policies and other related institutional changes. The list of questions can be found in Annexe 1, and a summary of the qualitative data collected is available in Section 4.2.

3.2 Making the Regional R&I Ecosystems More Open, Transparent and Democratic (O2)

The indicators selected to measure progress towards O2 are of three main categories: (i) process indicators (marked as PR in the body of the identifiers), which measured the quantity and quality of any actions taken and processes implemented; (ii) outcome indicators (marked as O in the body of the identifiers), which measured the tangible outcomes achieved; and (iii) perception indicators (marked as PE in the body of the identifiers), which measured perceived outcomes and changes in the perception and values of the engaged stakeholders.

After considering (i) the work done in Task 5.1⁹, (ii) the output of previous Horizon 2020 projects funded by the European Commission, such as MoRRI¹⁰, SUPER_MoRRI¹¹ and TeRRIFICA¹², (iii) the report from the Expert Group on Policy Indicators for RRI¹³, and (iv) the feedback received from RRI2SCALE consortium partners, the following indicators were selected.

Table 4: Indicators that measure progress towards O2

Identifier	Indicator	Collection
Fostering Public Engagement*		
PE.PR.4	Number of stakeholders believing that the group of people who participated in the discussion was sufficiently large to allow a meaningful discussion / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.2
PE.PR.5	Number of stakeholders believing that the group of people who participated in the discussion was adequately diverse to guarantee a transdisciplinary approach and allow a meaningful discussion / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.2
PE.PR.6	Number of people from each stakeholder group engaged in the RRI2SCALE workshops / Total number of stakeholders engaged	M2.2 + M2.3
PE.PR.7	Number of stakeholders who reported that they had sufficient background knowledge on the topics discussed to be able to participate in the RRI2SCALE workshops actively / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.2 + M2.3
PE.PR.8	Number of stakeholders who reported that the structure and the facilitation of the RRI2SCALE workshops allowed productive interactions between all participants and stimulated public debate / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.2
PE.O.1	Number of stakeholders who reported that the moderator(s) seriously considered their opinions, values, and expectations to be incorporated into future agendas and/or policies / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.3
PE.O.2	Number of stakeholders believing that the topic discussed was interesting and/or important for them / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.3

* Public Engagement (PE) fosters R&I processes that are collaborative and multi-actor, meaning that all societal actors work together during the whole process to align outcomes to society's values, needs, and expectations.

PE.O.3	Number of stakeholders believing that the RRI2SCALE workshops were a good opportunity for their region to advance towards collaborative decision-making and shared responsibility / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.3
PE.O.4	Number of stakeholders who reported that their participation helped them to understand current dilemmas in their region better / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.2
PE.O.5	Number of stakeholders who reported that RRI2SCALE workshops led or may lead to new partnerships, new networks or network coalitions / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.2
PE.PE.1	Number of stakeholders who reported that their participation helped them to increase their interest in policies affecting growth, innovation and equality in their region / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.3
PE.PE.2	Number of stakeholders (non-policymakers) who reported that their participation helped them to increase their trust in regional authorities / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.2
PE.PE.3	Number of stakeholders who reported that in the future they would more actively take part in similar discussions to co-design policies that affect growth, innovation and equality in their region / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.3
PE.PE.4	Number of academia who reported that they would undertake initiatives to increase public engagement in their future R&I activities in their organisation / Total number of researchers surveyed	M2.3
Providing Open Access*		
OA.PR.1	Number of scientific publications and datasets that were (or are being) created based on observations and findings from the RRI2SCALE activities	Direct observation
OA.PR.2	Number of the above scientific publications and datasets that were (or will be) made freely publicly available / Number of the above scientific publications and datasets	Direct observation
Improving Science Literacy (Science Education dimension) [†]		
SE.PR.1	Number of stakeholders who reported that their participation helped them to understand potential developments (e.g., technological, demographical and economic developments) that could affect their region by 2022 and beyond / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.2
SE.PR.2	Number of stakeholders believing that the RRI2SCALE workshops were a good opportunity for their region to advance towards awareness of the societal impact of science and technology / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.2

* Open access (OA) is the idea of making research results freely available to anyone that wants to access and re-use them. One of the main drivers of the OA would be to make publicly-funded research accessible to the general public.

[†] Science literacy is defined as the ability of citizens to read about, comprehend and express opinions about science, and contribute to "doing science".

SE.PE.1	Number of stakeholders who reported that their participation helped them to perceive new technologies such as intelligent cities, intelligent transport and intelligent energy as part of the solution in regional problems and dilemmas rather than the problem / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.2
SE.PE.2	Number of stakeholders who reported that in the future they would more actively search information about controversial technologies or read related articles and news / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.2
Promoting Gender Equality*		
GE.PR.1	Number of female participants in the RRI2SCALE workshops / Total number of stakeholders engaged	M2.2 + M2.3
GE.PR.2	Number of stakeholders who reported that the RRI2SCALE workshops were a gender-equal environment / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.2
GE.PR.3	Number of stakeholders who reported the absence of gender-inclusive language in the RRI2SCALE documents or encountered a biased attitude during the RRI2SCALE workshops / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.2
Considering Ethics [†]		
E.PR.1	Number of stakeholders who reported that the RRI2SCALE workshops complied with high research integrity standards and that good research practices were followed / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.2
E.O.1	Number of stakeholders believing that policy-makers should often organise similar discussions to allow future policies to reflect people's needs, preferences and concerns and be aligned with social values / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.3
E.O.3	Number of stakeholders who reported that similar discussions could increase citizens' trust in science and new technologies to solve regional problems / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.3
E.PE.1	Number of stakeholders who reported a better understanding of the importance of promoting ethical considerations and standards as a measure to improve R&I policy-making / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.2
E.PE.2	Number of stakeholders who reported that in the future they would more actively search information about ethically controversial research-endeavours or read related articles and news / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.2
Mainstreaming RRI in R&I Governance Framework [‡]		

* The gender equality (GE) dimension of RRI aims to set the R&I system free of gender bias.

[†] In the context of R&I, ethics (E) is "a common platform for deliberation and discussion of values in society based on perceptions of right and wrong, influenced by cultural norms and aimed at informing policy-making". This includes (i) Ethical Governance; (ii) Ethical deliberation; and (iii) Ethical reflection.

[‡] The Governance (GO) dimension of RRI refers to mainstreaming RRI in the governance framework of regional organisations. It entails all actions people take to foster and mainstream RRI practices and procedures in their organisations or towards other stakeholders.

GO.PR.1	Number of stakeholders believing that more people in their region would perceive discussions like the one they participated in as meaningful and happily participate in the future / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.3
GO.PE.1	Number of stakeholders believing that policy-makers should often organise discussions to consult citizens on their preferences and co-create solutions with them / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.3
GO.PE.2	Number of academia believing that universities in their region should organise similar discussions to co-create with citizens the purposes or design of their research activities / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.3

3.3 Stimulating Positive Developments Towards Addressing Regional & Global Challenges (O3)

The indicators within this subsection aimed to measure progress towards O3.

Table 5: Indicators that measure progress towards O3

Identifier	Indicator	Collection
Promoting Intelligent Technology Solutions		
E.O.3	Number of stakeholders who reported that similar discussions could increase citizens' trust in science and new technologies to solve regional problems / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.3
SDG.10.1	Number of stakeholders believing that policies developed through discussions will promote the use of new technologies (such as intelligent cities, intelligent transport and intelligent energy) to reduce inequality within the region / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.3
SP.DS.4	Number of policy-makers who reported that their participation helped them to perceive new technologies such as intelligent cities, intelligent transport and intelligent energy as part of the solution to regional problems and dilemmas rather than the problem / Total number of policy-makers surveyed	M2.2
SE.PE.1	Number of stakeholders who reported that their participation helped them to perceive new technologies such as intelligent cities, intelligent transport and intelligent energy as part of the solution to regional problems and dilemmas rather than the problem / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.2

Several of the following indicators are not dedicated to examining the outcomes induced by and rightfully attributed to the RRI2SCALE project since they may be affected by many random external factors (e.g., overall R&D&I efforts). However, they constitute an indication of the overarching trends in the region and can be used to monitor the broader set of developments taking place.

Table 6: Indicators that describe the overarching trends in the region

Objective	Identifier	Indicator	Collection tool
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Expediting Progress towards SDGs			
SDG 5: Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls	SDG.5.1	Percentage of female R&D personnel and researchers in all sectors	M3
	SDG.5.2	Percentage of female employees in technology and knowledge-intensive sectors	M3
	SDG.5.3	Percentage of young females that are neither in employment nor in education and training	M3
SDG 8: Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all	SDG.8.1	Number of stakeholders believing that policies developed through discussions will promote economic growth and spread its fruits fairly across society / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.3
	SDG.8.3	Economic growth (real growth rate of regional gross value added at basic prices - percentage change on the previous year)	M3
	SDG.8.4	Compensation of employees (i.e., aggregate compensation / thousand oh hours worked)	M3, M3
	SDG.8.7	Young people neither in employment nor in education and training	M3
	SDG.9.3	R&D personnel and researchers in all sectors	M3
	SDG.9.4	Gross domestic expenditure on R&D (GERD) in all sectors	M3
	SDG.9.5	Employment in technology and knowledge-intensive sectors	M3
SDG 10: Reduce inequality within and among countries	SDG.10.1	Number of stakeholders believing that policies developed through discussions will promote the use of new technologies (such as intelligent cities, intelligent transport and intelligent energy) to reduce inequality within the region / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.3
	SDG.10.2	People at risk of poverty or social exclusion	M3
	SDG.10.3	People living in households with very low work intensity	M3
SDG 11: Make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable	SDG.11.1	Life expectancy	M3
	SDG.11.4	Victims in road accidents (killed people)	M3
	SDG.11.6	Percentage of individuals who used the internet for interaction with public authorities	M3

Apart from the above, the RRI2SCALE project also aimed to contribute to the United Nations' SDGs 12, 16 and 17. Progress towards these objectives can be inferred through the following indicators.

Table 7: Additional SDGs that are monitored

SDGs	Indicators
12: Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns	SDG.10.1, SP.DS.4, SE.PE.1

16: Promote peaceful and inclusive societies for sustainable development, provide access to justice for all and build effective, accountable and inclusive institutions at all levels	SP.EP.2 - SP.EP.4, SP.EP.8, PE.PE.2, PE.PE.3
17: Strengthen the means of implementation and revitalise the global partnership for sustainable development	SP.DS.1, SP.EP.7, PE.O.5

4. Completed Indicators Database - Results

Section 4 is the outcome of the RRI2SCALE M&E framework. In other words, it meticulously describes the indicator values and presents a few interesting replies from questionnaire respondents. The reader may find results from all three data-collection methods. About method 2, in particular, 9 responses were received from the training questionnaire (M2.1), more than 15 replies from the SES questionnaire (M2.2) and more than 30 replies from the co-creation workshop questionnaire (M2.3). The results can also be found on [Zenodo](#) (Monitoring results).

4.1 Quantitative Monitoring Results

4.1.1 *Transforming and Opening Up the R&I Policy-Making Processes of the Four Regional Authorities (01)*

Table 8: Results pertinent to 01

Identifier	Indicator	Collection	Overall
Adopting R&I Policy-Making Methods that Look into the Future			
SP.DS.1	Number of policy-makers who reported a better understanding of the importance of informing policy-makers about estimations on future developments (e.g., technological, demographical and research developments) in their region before engaging in any R&I policy-making process / Total number of policy-makers surveyed	M2.1	78%*
SP.DS.2	Number of policy-makers reported that their participation in the RRI2SCALE training helped them organise the multistakeholder dialogue (or the Scenario Exploration System - SES session, as commonly called) of their region / Total number of policy-makers surveyed	M2.1	67%
SP.DS.3	Number of policy-makers reported that their participation in the SES session contributed to appreciating the positions of different stakeholders / Total number of policy-makers surveyed	M2.2	100%

* To measure this indicator, survey respondents were asked the following question: "Do you believe that familiarising policy-makers with estimations about future developments (e.g., technological, demographical and research developments) in their region is crucial for their strategic planning process?" Potential answers were: (i) Very much; (ii) Somewhat; (iii) Neutral; (iv) Not really; (v) Not at all; and (vi) Undecided. The outcome of the indicator was calculated by aggregating those who replied "Very much" and "Somewhat". The values of the remaining indicators are calculated similarly. The exact phrasing of the questions can be found in the questionnaires in Annexes.

SP.DS.4	Number of policy-makers reported that their participation helped them to perceive new technologies such as intelligent cities, intelligent transport and intelligent energy as part of the solution to regional problems and dilemmas rather than the problem / Total number of policy-makers surveyed	M2.2	57%
SP.DS.5	Number of policy-makers reported that their participation helped them to understand potential developments (e.g., technological, demographical and economic developments) that could affect their region by 2022 and beyond / Total number of policy-makers surveyed	M2.2	57%
Embodying RRI Practices into the R&I Policy-Making Process and Governance Framework			
SP.EP.1	Number of policy-makers reported the RRI2SCALE training familiarised them with practices to capture weak societal signals (e.g., people's feelings) when they organise strategic planning processes / Total number of policy-makers surveyed	M2.1	56%
SP.EP.2	Number of policy-makers reported a better understanding of the importance of promoting multi-stakeholder engagement in the region's R&I policy-making as a measure to democratise decision-making / Total number of policy-makers surveyed	M2.3	66%
SP.EP.3	Number of policy-makers reported that they would undertake initiatives to increase public engagement in the strategic planning of their region / Total number of policy-makers surveyed	M2.3	83%
SP.EP.4	Number of policy-makers reported a better understanding of the importance of considering ethics and social values as a measure to achieve higher acceptance of R&I-related public policies / Total number of policy-makers surveyed	M2.2	71%
SP.EP.5	Number of policy-makers reported the RRI2SCALE training familiarised them with practices to encourage interactivens among stakeholders when they organise strategic planning processes / Total number of policy-makers surveyed	M2.1	100%
SP.EP.7	Number of policy-makers reported that their participation helped them to understand current dilemmas in their region better / Total number of policy-makers surveyed	M2.2	71%
SP.EP.8	Number of policy-makers reported a better understanding of how to design and implement participatory processes / Total number of policy-makers surveyed	M2.1	33%
Making Changes Sustainable Beyond the Lifetime of the Project			
SP.SC.2	Number of regional authorities reported that the higher-level policy-makers of their regions are aware of the RRI concept / Total number of regional authorities	M1	50%
SP.SC.3	Number of regional authorities reported that the higher-level policy-makers consider the RRI concept as crucial for the R&I ecosystem and the prosperity of their region / Total number of regional authorities	M1	0%

SP.SC.4	Number of regional authorities reported that the tools and methods introduced by the RRI2SCALE project, such as the training on stakeholder dialogues, the SES game, the agendas and roadmaps, have been communicated to higher-level policy-makers to consider their permanent or extended use / Total number of regional authorities	M1	50%
SP.SC.5	Number of regional authorities reported that higher-level policy-makers consider the tools and methods introduced by the RRI2SCALE project as meaningful and plan to use them in the future / Total number of regional authorities	M1	0%

4.1.2 Making the Regional R&I Ecosystems More Open, Transparent and Democratic (O2)

Table 9: Results pertinent to O2

Identifier	Indicator	Collection	Vestland	Overijssel	Kríti	Galicia	Overall
Fostering Public Engagement							
PE.PR.4	Number of stakeholders believing that the group of people who participated in the discussion was sufficiently large to allow a meaningful discussion / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.2	83%	100%	80%	100%	88%
PE.PR.5	Number of stakeholders believing that the group of people who participated in the discussion was adequately diverse to guarantee a transdisciplinary approach and allow a meaningful discussion / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.2	67%	50%	100%	75%	76%
PE.PR.7	Number of stakeholders who reported that they had sufficient background knowledge on the topics discussed to be able to participate in the RRI2SCALE workshops actively / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.2 + M2.3	80%	100%	75%	80%	83%
PE.PR.8	Number of stakeholders who reported that the structure and the facilitation of the RRI2SCALE workshops allowed productive interactions between all participants and stimulated public debate / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.2	100%	100%	100%	75%	94%
PE.O.1	Number of stakeholders who reported that the moderator(s) seriously considered their opinions, values, and expectations to be incorporated into future agendas and/or policies / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.3	100%	80%	100%	100%	95%

PE.O.2	Number of stakeholders believing that the topic discussed was interesting and/or important for them / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.3	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
PE.O.3	Number of stakeholders believing that the RRI2SCALE workshops were a good opportunity for their region to advance towards collaborative decision-making and shared responsibility / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.3	100%	80%	100%	100%	95%
PE.O.4	Number of stakeholders who reported that their participation helped them to understand current dilemmas in their region better / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.2	67%	50%	80%	0%	53%
PE.O.5	Number of stakeholders who reported that RRI2SCALE workshops led or may lead to new partnerships, new networks or network coalitions / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.2	17%	100%	100%	75%	65%
PE.PE.1	Number of stakeholders who reported that their participation helped them to increase their interest in policies affecting growth, innovation and equality in their region / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.3	100%	100%	87%	80%	90%
PE.PE.2	Number of stakeholders (non-policymakers) who reported that their participation helped them to increase their trust in regional authorities / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.2	0%	0%	100%	25%	35%
PE.PE.3	Number of stakeholders who reported that in the future they would more actively take part in similar discussions to co-design policies that affect growth, innovation and equality in their region / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.3	50%	100%	93%	100%	92%
PE.PE.4	Number of academia who reported that they would undertake initiatives to increase public engagement in their future R&I activities in their organisation / Total number of researchers surveyed	M2.3	N/A				90%
PE.PR.6	Number of people from academia engaged in the RRI2SCALE workshops / Total number of stakeholders engaged	M2.2 + M2.3	10%	83%	10%	39%	33%
	Number of people from government engaged in the RRI2SCALE workshops / Total number of stakeholders engaged		60%	17%	55%	38%	44%

	Number of people from business engaged in the RRI2SCALE workshops / Total number of stakeholders engaged		10%	0%	5%	15%	7%
	Number of people from civil society engaged in the RRI2SCALE workshops / Total number of stakeholders engaged		0%	0%	15%	8%	7%
	Number of other stakeholders (e.g., observers, media) engaged in the RRI2SCALE workshops / Total number of stakeholders engaged		20%	0%	15%	0%	6%
Providing Open Access							
OA.PR.1	Number of scientific publications and datasets that were (or are being) created based on observations and findings from the RRI2SCALE activities	Direct observation	N/A				8
OA.PR.2	Number of the above scientific publications and datasets that were (or will be) made freely publicly available / Number of the above scientific publications and datasets	Direct observation	N/A				100%
Improving Science Literacy (Science Education dimension)							
SE.PR.1	Number of stakeholders who reported that their participation helped them to understand potential developments (e.g., technological, demographical and economic developments) that could affect their region by 2022 and beyond / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.2	67%	100%	60%	50%	65%
SE.PR.2	Number of stakeholders believing that the RRI2SCALE workshops were a good opportunity for their region to advance towards awareness of the societal impact of science and technology / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.2	83%	100%	80%	50%	76%
SE.PE.1	Number of stakeholders who reported that their participation helped them to perceive new technologies such as intelligent cities, intelligent transport and intelligent energy as part of the solution in regional problems and dilemmas rather than the problem / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.2	50%	50%	60%	0%	41%

SE.PE.2	Number of stakeholders who reported that in the future they would more actively search information about controversial technologies or read related articles and news / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.2	33%	0%	60%	0%	29%
Promoting Gender Equality							
GE.PR.1	Number of female participants in the RRI2SCALE workshops / Total number of stakeholders engaged	M2.2 + M2.3	70%	83%	58%	67%	68%
GE.PR.2	Number of stakeholders who reported that the RRI2SCALE workshops were a gender-equal environment / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.2	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
GE.PR.3	Number of stakeholders who reported the absence of gender-inclusive language in the RRI2SCALE documents or encountered a biased attitude during the RRI2SCALE workshops / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.2	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Considering Ethics							
E.PR.1	Number of stakeholders who reported that the RRI2SCALE workshops complied with high research integrity standards and that good research practices were followed / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.2	83%	100%	100%	75%	88%
E.O.1	Number of stakeholders believing that policy-makers should often organise similar discussions to allow future policies to reflect people's needs, preferences and concerns and be aligned with social values / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.3	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
E.O.3	Number of stakeholders who reported that similar discussions could increase citizens' trust in science and new technologies to solve regional problems / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.3	100%	100%	93%	91%	95%
E.PE.1	Number of stakeholders who reported a better understanding of the importance of promoting ethical considerations and standards as a measure to improve R&I policy-making / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.2	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

E.PE.2	Number of stakeholders who reported that in the future they would more actively search information about ethically controversial research-endeavours or read related articles and news / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.2	50%	50%	20%	0%	29%
Mainstreaming RRI in R&I Governance Framework							
GO.PR.1	Number of stakeholders believing that more people in their region would perceive discussions like the one they participated in as meaningful and happily participate in the future / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.3	50%	80%	87%	82%	80%
GO.PE.1	Number of stakeholders believing that policy-makers should often organise discussions to consult citizens on their preferences and co-create solutions with them / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.3	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
GO.PE.2	Number of academia believing that universities in their region should organise similar discussions to co-create with citizens the purposes or design of their research activities / Total number of academia surveyed	M2.3	N/A				71%

4.1.3 Stimulating Positive Developments Towards Addressing Regional & Global Challenges (O3)

Table 10: Results pertinent to O3

Identifier	Indicator	Collection	Vestland	Overijssel	Kriti	Galicia	Overall
Promoting Intelligent Technology Solutions							
E.O.3	Number of stakeholders who reported that similar discussions could increase citizens' trust in science and new technologies to solve regional problems / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.3	100%	100%	93%	91%	95%
SDG.10.1	Number of stakeholders believing that policies developed through discussions will promote the use of new technologies (such as intelligent cities, intelligent transport and intelligent energy) to reduce inequality within the region / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.3	100%	50%	86%	82%	77%

SP.DS.4	Number of policy-makers who reported that their participation helped them to perceive new technologies such as intelligent cities, intelligent transport and intelligent energy as part of the solution to regional problems and dilemmas rather than the problem / Total number of policy-makers surveyed	M2.2	N/A				57%
SE.PE.1	Number of stakeholders who reported that their participation helped them to perceive new technologies such as intelligent cities, intelligent transport and intelligent energy as part of the solution to regional problems and dilemmas rather than the problem / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.2	50%	50%	60%	0%	41%
SDG.8.1	Number of stakeholders believing that the developed agendas and roadmaps, if materialise, will promote economic growth and spread its fruits fairly across society / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.3	75%	60%	87%	82%	78%
SDG.10.1	Number of stakeholders believing that the developed agendas and roadmaps, if materialise, will promote the use of new technologies (such as intelligent cities, intelligent transport and intelligent energy) to reduce inequality within the region / Total number of stakeholders surveyed	M2.3	100%	50%	86%	82%	77%

Many of the following results are based on Eurostat data, which was available only for 2019. The outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic is a potential explanation for this delay. Government restrictions imposed on the movement of people and non-essential economic activities had implications for the quality and availability of many data sources.¹⁴

Table 11: Overarching trends in the regions

Identifier	Indicator	Collection	Vestland	Overijssel	Kriti	Galicia	Average	Comment
Expediting Progress towards SDGs								
SDG.5.1	Percentage of female R&D personnel and researchers in all sectors	M3	N/A	N/A	41%	41%	41%	available only at country level, 2019

SDG.5.2	Percentage of female employees in technology and knowledge-intensive sectors	M3	35%	24%	47%	34%	35%	2016;2020; 2019;2020
SDG.5.3	Percentage of young females that are neither in employment nor in education and training	M3	4.2%	4.8%	13.0%	8.5%	8%	2016;2020; 2020;2020
SDG.8.3	Economic growth (real growth rate of regional gross value added at basic prices - percentage change on the previous year)	M3	N/A	7.1%	-11.9%	-0.6%	-1.8%	2020
SDG.8.4	Compensation of employees (i.e., aggregate compensation / thousand oh hours worked)	M3 , M3	N/A	€25.8	€5.5	€15.8	€15.7	2019;2019; 2020
SDG.8.7	Young people neither in employment nor in education and training	M3	N/A	4.7%	12.2%	9.2%	8.7%	2020
SDG.9.3	R&D personnel and researchers in all sectors	M3	7.6	N/A	53.9	231	98	in million, 2019
SDG.9.4	Gross domestic expenditure on R&D (GERD) in all sectors	M3	1213	N/A	141	627	660	in million, 2019
SDG.9.5	Employment in technology and knowledge-intensive sectors	M3	11	21	3	31.5	17	in thousand, 2016;2020; 2019;2020
SDG.10.2	People at risk of poverty or social exclusion	M3	20%	15%	27%	26%	22%	2020
SDG.10.3	People living in households with very low work intensity	M3	10%	8%	9%	9%	9%	2020
SDG.11.1	Life expectancy	M3	83,6	81.2	82.6	83.7	83	2019;2020; 2020;2020
SDG.11.4	Victims in road accidents (people killed)	M3	21	57	49	127	64	2019
SDG.11.6	Percentage of individuals who used the internet for interaction with public authorities	M3	93%	86%	51%	64%	74%	2020;2021; 2021;2021

4.2 Qualitative Monitoring Results

4.2.1 Regional Reports (M1)

Regional authorities filled in a regional report every four months beginning from February 2022. This report included a few open-ended questions which aimed to capture and regularly monitor the integration of RRI practices into regional authorities' R&I governance frameworks and policies and other related institutional changes. Based on the replies received, a summary of each region's situation and progress is provided below.

Table 12: The situation and the progress in Vestland

	Vestland County Council	<p>February 2022: The last time that the Vestland regional authority carried out an R&I policy-making process with some sort of public engagement was in 2021 when an entrepreneurial discovery process to identify key areas for green innovation projects was held. People from municipalities, regional development agencies, and other stakeholders in the quadruple helix were invited to participate. Their key motivation was the will to take a direct part in the decision-making process relevant to their business.</p> <p>The regional authority of Vestland promotes Open Access. For instance, it has developed a web portal with interactive plug-ins where the public can gain insights on several topics. Also, it promotes science literacy by funding some relevant local initiatives (e.g., a science hub for after school and a science activity centre). At the same time, Vestland has an Equality Plan connected to the public health plan. According to it, at least 40% of board members of businesses and political bodies must be women. Finally, Vestland has in place policy documents to safeguard ethical standards.</p> <p>Among the challenges to embedding RRI, the Vestland region mentioned that the processes involving many stakeholders are complex and often demand administrative capacity and skills. E.g., remembering and identifying stakeholders outside the normal contact points. Thus, regions need to buy services from external consultants, which significantly raises costs.</p> <p>June 2022: The regional authorities were also asked to mention any past decisions taken (or policies adopted) by the local or regional authority that were not very successful due to the lack of public involvement in the decision-making process. The regional authority of Vestland indicated the planning for Renewable Energy. In particular, it reported that the initial stages of the regional plan for renewable energy were decided solely by the committee for business development. After the decision was taken, some debates led to material changes to the plan, especially regarding wind turbines.</p> <p>October 2022: Similarly, the decision over the digitalisation of bus tickets could have been better if citizens had been consulted beforehand. When ticketing moved to an App, the older citizens felt excluded. The situation was remedied with the option to buy tickets via text message and later with bank terminals on board all buses.</p>
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Table 13: The situation and the progress in Overijssel

	Overijssel	<p>February 2022: The last time the Overijssel regional authority carried out an R&I policy-making process with some sort of public engagement was when developing the regional energy strategy (RES 1.0) covering the technical plans for the future energy transition. About 10 members from 25 local municipal councils (equal to 250 people) participated, primarily motivated by personal and professional interests.</p>
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Open data is a standard policy in the Netherlands. There is a web portal to share province data, mainly geo-data. Also, Overijssel promotes science literacy. Citizen science projects have been started, e.g., in collaboration with UT. At the same time, a balance between the female and male committee and council members is strived for, as well as in the selection of employees. Finally, formal policy documents on ethics were recently (2021) updated to include data ethics.

Among the challenges to embedding RRI, the Overijssel region mentioned including non-usual suspects in the participatory processes. The Stakeholders benefitting from regulations are already included and participate actively. But, other groups, like citizens or NGOs, are more difficult to involve, except when the policy measures align with their interests.

June 2022: The regional authorities were also asked to mention any past decisions taken (or policies adopted) by the local or regional authority that were not very successful due to the lack of public involvement in the decision-making process. The regional authority of Overijssel indicated the Regional Energy Strategies. They were drafted without direct inhabitants' input but through consultations with political councils of all the municipalities. This approach increases the risk of the 'NIMBY' phenomena in future stages of policy implementation. Also, it may lie behind hot debates with farmers over higher nitrogen emission & deposition requirements. And finally, it may lead to societal unrest in rural areas.

October 2022: The Overijssel region is moving from Regional Energy Strategy v1.0 to v2.0. Municipal Councils have to assign locations for (large) windmills. Only 3 municipalities are consulting citizens. Citizen involvement varies. Civic ownership of 50% of windmills is made compulsory. Lesson learnt: Citizen or civic involvement in regional innovation needs to be specific, time-/place-bound, with benefits to participating volunteers to spend their time and sincere commitment from companies and/or knowledge partners to responsible innovation.

Table 14: The situation and the progress in Kriti

Περιφέρεια Κρήτης

Region of Crete

February 2022: The last time that the Kriti regional authority carried out an R&I policy-making process with some sort of public engagement was in 2021 when the review of the RIS3Crete Strategy in the framework of the new programming period 2021-2027 took place. About 75 stakeholders from public/private bodies, businesses and academia participated. They were motivated to contribute based on their perspective, experience, and knowledge.

The regional authority of Kriti promotes Open Access. For instance, it has developed an online platform to provide stakeholders with geospatial information. Also, it promotes science literacy by organising (i) educational events open to the public, (ii) educational/ training activities and programs related to STEM, and (iii) seminars for various issues to upgrade the knowledge of SMEs. At the same time, Kriti founded the Independent Equality Office. The office collects and processes relevant data and evaluates regional policies and actions. In addition, the region has a Regional Committee for Gender Equality that prepares the Regional Equality Plan. Finally, Kriti has a Behavior & Ethics Guide for civil servants, which explains how they should behave when interacting with citizens and handling citizen cases.

Kriti's regional authority has also undertaken the initiative to build an Innovation Business Observatory – IBO. It aims to (i) interconnect businesses with research & academic institutions; (ii) map the innovation ecosystem of the Kriti Region; (iii) boost R&I within our institutions, students and businesses. In February 2022, a pilot platform was created for data management between business & academia.

Among the challenges to embedding RRI, the Kriti region mentioned that RRI is a new concept and quite complicated. Also, due to the complexity of the issues discussed in the participatory processes (e.g., infrastructure projects and innovation), the potential impacts must be communicated in simple terms for the public & stakeholders to understand the issue & engage actively.

June 2022: The regional authorities were also asked to mention any past decisions taken (or policies adopted) by the local or regional authority that were not very successful due to the lack of public involvement in the decision-making process. The regional authority of Kriti indicated the process of defining the NATURA protection zones. More specifically, in Kriti, the Regional Council decided to protect natural ecosystems & biodiversity. So, it forbade new constructions and farming activities in several free lands that needed protection. Then, residents (people, farmers, agents, and businesses) of this area (which is underdeveloped in terms of tourism or agriculture but with natural wealth) claimed the decision limits human activities and the development of tourism and agriculture. Until the current report was drafted, opposition and social discontent remained.

October 2022: The Environmental Impact Assessment Study for the Upgrade of the VOAK (National Highway in the Island of Crete) was on public consultation from late July to early September 2022. It was a typical public engagement process with several stakeholders but no actual citizen involvement.

Table 15: The situation and the progress in Galicia

**XUNTA
DE GALICIA**

February 2022: The last time the Galicia regional authority carried out an R&I policy-making process with some sort of public engagement was in 2021 when the design and elaboration of the regional S3 took place. More than 250 people from triple helix participated. These people collaborate with the region regularly, as regional decisions are relevant to their businesses.

The regional authority of Galicia promotes Open Access. For instance, the developments and results of projects using public funds are shared openly. Also, it promotes science literacy by funding initiatives such as Science Nights and organising outdoor shows and competitions to facilitate citizens involvement in innovation. At the same time, regional government regulations include provisions relevant to gender equality. Finally, the Health Department of the regional government has in place the Galician Network of Research Ethics Committees (CEImG).

June 2022: The regional authorities were also asked to mention any past decisions taken (or policies adopted) by the local or regional authority that were not very successful due to the lack of public involvement in the decision-making process. The regional authority of Galicia indicated the Fish-farming Action Plan. According to GAIN, the Action Plan was designed and elaborated "indoors" by the regional government, with no participation of any other stakeholders. And thus, later, when it was about to be passed in the parliament, the fishing sector clearly stated their opposition to the plan and managed to stop it.

October 2022: The Galician regional authority mentioned that RRI2SCALE helped them to raise awareness about RRI among policy-makers in their region. And there is the intention to follow RRI principles as a mechanism to support the implementation of the new RIS3 when approved. In October, an Action Plan to promote RRI in marine sectors was presented by the regional government. Also, two new initiatives were presented for 2023: scientific cinema sessions for families and innovation summer camps for kids (one week duration per camp).

4.2.2 Feedback Questionnaires (M2.2, M2.3)

The questionnaires shared with regional stakeholders included a few open-ended questions to get descriptive answers and accommodate an extensive range of different responses from respondents. Within the current subsection, the most insightful replies and comments are presented.

Table 16: Performance and impact of the SES

#	Q.1.1: Comments by participants
1	I liked the scenario descriptions and the raising of multiple voices the most. I think the power distribution in terms of resources available to the stakeholders was a weak part because it presumed the power distribution instead of leaving it open to the game dynamics. I understand that this could be a feature of the SES game, but I think for the SES game to fit the purposes of MS dialogues, the power distribution composition should not be presumed beforehand.
2	Vivid discussions and tendency to cooperate. Time constraints (3 hrs is still short for two scenarios).
3	I liked the discussions after we played out different scenarios. However, the scenarios were somewhat complex, which made it difficult to follow all the discussions and decision-making.
4	(I liked the fact) that the game amplified the roles of the different actors, showing their role in society and policy.
5	Innovative approach of discussion that is very unexpected for local authorities in Greece as a tool. But I would prefer a more simple board that would need fewer explanations and preparation. Most importantly, the language should be Greek so that more participants can express themselves better and will have the incentive to participate.
6	I did not see any marked difference between the two extreme scenarios in the responses to the participants, so I lost the point of presenting two opposing scenarios for the future.
7	It was important that dialogue and cooperation took place between the participants. The time we were given was short. I would also like more participants to have more views.
8	New process that I would like to learn more about. Maybe easier to do the "game" physically and not digitally
9	I liked that the game brought up discussion and that each participant could present their opinions and values. I would have liked it if the discussion had continued after each participant used their action card and tokens. Maybe use more time on that and have maybe fewer rounds. Like having two rounds instead of three. I liked how the action cards helped the players to start the discussion.

Table 17: Performance and impact of the co-creation workshop

#	Q.2.1: Comments by participants
1	The discussion was very relevant due to the variety of agents or actors represented in the group. The allocated time for the debate was short.
2	Share with other members in the meeting real experiences and needs, and also expectations regarding not only about RRI but also regarding interaction and communication among administration and citizens. Weak part: too much time for topic introduction, but not enough time for discussion and to share and debate about conclusions of both working groups.

3	It was positive to discuss the topic with a group of people of different profiles and professions. It could be improved by bringing a representative of a public authority that had implemented good practices and showing its success story.
4	Most liked: the enthusiasm of the participants. Weak part: many issues remained unsaid due to the lack of time
5	The best part is the discussions between public administrations, citizens and companies. The weakest, non enough time.
6	Pros: high level of discussion & participation, Cons: 1. Discussion not related to R&D, 2. Presentations & leaflets should be more understandable, 3. Needed more time/info for the principles of the project and more time for the discussion afterwards

5. Conclusion

The RRI2SCALE M&E framework was designed to measure key RRI2SCALE activities' performance and impact. About 100 indicators were closely monitored, and four questionnaires/reports were shared with more than 50 regional stakeholders. The outcome of this exercise was to develop the RRI2SCALE Indicators Database, which includes a great range of data and insights to feed into the project's next steps. Task 5.3 further analyses and interprets the data collected/generated. And based on this data, it evaluates the progress toward achieving key project objectives, such as addressing Regional Dilemmas.

Annexes

Annexe 1 – Regional Report (M1)

REGIONAL REPORT

The purpose of this report is to capture and regularly monitor the integration of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) practices into the Research and Innovation (R&I) governance frameworks and policies of regional authorities. It must be completed by the person representing each regional authority to the RRI2SCALE consortium every four months, beginning from February 2022. The collected answers will improve our understanding of the regional context and, thus, improve the RRI2SCALE approach and activities.

Before proceeding to the questions, reading the following glossary may be helpful to you. For any further clarifications, please don't hesitate to contact Task 5.2 leader (Q-PLAN) at mangelidou@qplan-intl.gr.

- **Research and innovation (R&I)** can be defined as the process of producing new knowledge and the conception and application of better solutions that meet new requirements, unarticulated needs, or existing market needs and lead a region to gain a competitive advantage.
- **R&I ecosystem** is the term used to describe the large number and diverse nature of participants and resources necessary for R&I. These include entrepreneurs, investors, researchers, university faculties, venture capitalists, business development, and other technical service providers.
- **Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)** is a term used to describe scientific research and technological development processes that consider effects and potential impacts on the environment and society. RRI implies that societal actors (researchers, citizens, policy-makers, businesses, etc.) work together during the whole R&I process to align better the R&I activities and outcomes with society's values, needs, and expectations.
- **R&I policy-making process**, in the context of this questionnaire, is defined as any process (e.g., workshop, discussion, committee, consultation and online deliberation) held to decide upon and design policies affecting the research and innovation activities taking place within a region. Indicative examples of R&I policy-making processes are: (i) the entrepreneurial discovery process organised to design the Smart Specialisation Strategy of a region; (ii) a formal discussion between policy-makers on the region's strategic plans; and (iii) a consultation on adopting new technologies, such as a platform, that help the regional authority easier communicate with citizens.

What is your name? *It is highly recommended that always the same person files the report to facilitate comparisons between different periods.*

Q.4.1: Apart from the RRI2SCALE activities, when was it the last time your organisation carried out an R&I policy-making process with some sort of public engagement? *If no such process has taken place since <month that the last regional report was filled in>, please just write "No such process carried out recently".*

If no such process has taken place since <month that the last regional report was filled in>, please ignore the following five questions (Q.4.2-Q.4.6). Otherwise, please reply to them.

Q.4.2: In the above process, what model of public engagement was selected (Public communication/ Public activism/ Public consultation/ Public deliberation/ Public participation)*?

Q.4.3: In the above process, how many people participated and how were they selected? Also, how did you ensure the diversity of the stakeholder group?

Q.4.4: Why do you think these people were eager/incentivised to participate in the above process? Do you generally have strategies and formalised mechanisms in your organisation to engage stakeholders? For example, does your region have a public relations office or a digital marketing manager?

Q.4.5: Which main challenges does your organisation face when engaging the public in an R&I policy-making process?

Q.4.6: Did you employ any measures to encourage interactiveness among participants, collaborative decision-making, and shared responsibility in the above process? If yes, then could you briefly describe them? *For example, did you somehow ensure a gender-equal environment, and did you provide participants with sufficient background knowledge on the topics discussed?*

* (i) Public communication – the aim is to inform and/or educate citizens; (ii) Public activism – the aim is to inform decision-makers and create awareness to influence decision-making processes; (iii) Public consultation – the aim is to inform decision-makers about public opinions on certain topics; (iv) Public deliberation – the aim is to facilitate group deliberation on policy issues, where the outcome may impact decision-making; and (v) Public participation – the aim is to assign partly or full decision-making power to citizens on policy issues.

Q.4.7: What is your role within your organisation? For example, do you exclusively work on research projects such as the RRI2SCALE project, or do you also participate in a decision-making body? Are you a political person or a civil servant? Would you please describe your current job position?

#	Identifier	Question	Very much	Some what	Undecided	Not really	Not at all
1	SP. SC.2	Are the higher-level policy-makers of your region aware of the RRI concept?					
2	SP. SC.3	Do higher-level policy-makers consider the RRI concept as crucial for the R&I ecosystem and the prosperity of your region? (if applicable)					
3	SP. SC.4	Have any of the tools and methods introduced by the RRI2SCALE project, such as the training on stakeholder dialogues, the SES game, the agendas and roadmaps, been communicated by you to higher-level policy-makers to consider their permanent or extended use?					
4	SP. SC.5	Do higher-level policy-makers consider the tools and methods introduced by the RRI2SCALE project as meaningful and plan to use them in the future? (if applicable)					

Q.4.8: Does your organisation currently promotes open access to knowledge and data (e.g., platforms that make available data generated by the regional and local IoT devices)? If yes, then how? *If nothing has changed since <month that the last regional report was filled in>, please just write "nothing changed".*

Q.4.9: Does your organisation take any actions to improve science literacy in the region (e.g., initiatives that educate citizens of all ages about science or generate awareness of science-related issues and a positive image of science)? If yes, then what exactly? *If nothing has changed since <month that the last regional report was filled in>, please just write "nothing changed".*

Q.4.10: Does your organisation take any actions and implement any standards or policies to minimise gender inequality within its governance framework (e.g., requirements for equal representation of both genders in decision-making bodies)? If yes, then what is it? *If nothing has changed since <month that the last regional report was filled in>, please just write "nothing changed".*

Q.4.11: Does your organisation have in place any mechanism to safeguard ethical standards (e.g., a research ethics committee or a research integrity office). If yes, then what is it? *If nothing has changed since <month that the last regional report was filled in>, please just write "nothing changed".*

Q.4.12: Does your organisation set in place any process to monitor and evaluate the societal, democratic, economic and scientific impact of its policies? If yes, then what is it? *If nothing has changed since <month that the last regional report was filled in>, please just write "nothing changed".*

Q.4.13: Apart from the above, did your organisation recently undertake any other initiatives (e.g., institutional changes) to embed RRI practices into its governance framework? If yes, then could you please describe them? *Examples of such initiatives could be (i) the adoption of new forms of decision-making; (ii) employing methodologies for the engagement of the quadrable helix stakeholders, (iii) a more meaningful public engagement into R&I policy-making processes, and (iv) measures to ensure shared responsibility and ownership of the introduced policies. If nothing has changed since <month that the last regional report was filled in>, please just write "nothing changed".*

Q.4.14: If you positively replied to the above question, then please reply also to this one. Otherwise, please ignore it. Did the RRI2SCALE project contribute in any way to the above initiatives/institutional changes?

Q.4.15: What barriers to embodying RRI practices to your organisation's governance framework have you identified? *If nothing has changed since <month that the last regional report was filled in>, please just write "nothing changed".*

Q.4.16: Would you like to make any suggestions on how RRI2SCALE could improve its current approach, especially when it comes to (i) embodying RRI practices to your organisation's governance framework; and (ii) addressing the Regional Dilemmas of your region? *If nothing has changed since <month that the last regional report was filled in>, please just write "nothing changed".*

Q.4.17: Did any of the stakeholders who participated in the RRI2SCALE activities and workshops inform you that he/she has undertaken any initiative to embed RRI practices into the governance framework of his/her organisation? *If nothing has changed since <month that the last regional report was filled in>, please just write "nothing changed".*

Q.4.18: What issues did you encounter when collecting the above data (e.g., Information silos)?

The regional reports for June and October 2022 also included the following two questions.

Q.4.19: Do you think that the tools and methods introduced by the RRI2SCALE project (such as the training on stakeholder dialogues, the SES, the agendas and roadmaps) would be useful and feasible to be used by your region in the future? If yes, could you provide a few examples? For example, could the SES be used in the preparatory stages of an entrepreneurial discovery process to identify key policy intervention areas? *If nothing has changed since <month that the last regional report was filled in>, please just write "nothing changed".*

Q.4.20: Can you recall in your memory any decision taken (or policy adopted) by the local or regional authority that turned out to not be very successful? Would the situation be different if the public had participated in the decision-making process? For example, electrifying the bus fleet faced great opposition because it overlooked the fact that electric buses can not travel far enough to service remote villages. *If nothing has changed since <month that the last regional report was filled in>, please just write "nothing changed".*

Annexe 2 – Training Questionnaire (M2.1)

Title: Evaluation of the training on the implementation of stakeholder dialogues

Description: The current questionnaire aims to measure the impact of the RRI2SCALE training on implementing stakeholder dialogues that took place last autumn.

#	Identifier	Question	Very much	Some what	Neutral	Not really	Not at all	Undecided
1	SP.DS.2	Did your participation in the RRI2SCALE training help you to organise the multistakeholder dialogue (or the Scenario Exploration System - SES session, as commonly called) of your region?						
2	SP.EP.8	Did your participation in the RRI2SCALE training improve your skills to better design and implement strategic planning processes with public engagement?						
3	SP.EP.5	Did the RRI2SCALE training familiarise you with practices to encourage interactiveness among stakeholders when you organise strategic planning processes?						
4	SP.EP.1	Did the RRI2SCALE training familiarise you with practices to capture weak societal signals (e.g., people's feelings) when you organise strategic planning processes?						
5	SP.DS.1	Do you believe that familiarising policy-makers with estimations about future developments (e.g., technological, demographical and research developments) in their region is crucial for their strategic planning process?						

Do you represent an organisation that is part of the RRI2SCALE consortium?

- Yes
- No
- Other

Thank you for your feedback!

Annexe 3 - SES Questionnaire (M2.2)

Title: Regional multi-stakeholder dialogue (SES session) evaluation form

Description: The current questionnaire aims to measure the performance and impact of the RRI2SCALE regional multi-stakeholder dialogue (or the Scenario Exploration System - SES, as commonly called) that took place in each pilot region.

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

We are **< Insert Regional Authority Name >** and we are contacting you in the framework of RRI2SCALE, a project funded by the European Union under the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation. A detailed description of how we handle personal data is presented in the Privacy Policy that accompanies this Consent Form.

Project: RRI2SCALE - Responsible Research and Innovation Ecosystems at Regional Scale for Intelligent Cities, Transport and Energy (GA Number 872526).

Partner: Organisation name: **< Insert Regional Authority Name >**

Address: **< Insert Regional Authority Address >**

Phone: **< Insert Regional Authority Phone >**

E-mail: **< Insert Regional Authority Generic E-mail Address >**

Responsible persons: 1. Project Manager: **< Insert Name >** (**< Insert email >**)

2. Data Protection Officer: **< Insert Name >** (**< Insert email >**)

What do we need from you?

We need you to participate in a short survey. It won't take you more than 7 minutes. Your replies will help us to evaluate the performance and impact of the key project activities. In this context, we need to process some of your personal data:

- Some basic demographics (gender, stakeholder group);

What will we do with your data?

The project's deliverables that the survey will derive will not include your personal data or any other information that could identify you. However, we are obliged to grant access to your data to:

- EU officials such as our Project Officer for purposes related to the project's evaluation;
- EU agencies and other authorities for project auditing purposes.

How can you withdraw your consent?

You can withdraw your consent at any time by communicating by email or on the phone with the responsible persons listed above.

I hereby give my consent to the processing of my personal data needed for:

#	Consent Subject	Tick box
1	My participation in a survey that will be carried out by RRI2SCALE to evaluate the performance and impact of key project activities, such as workshops and other materials.	

#	Identifier	Question	Very much	Some what	Neutr al	Not really	Not at all	Unde cided
1	PE.PR.4	Do you believe that the group of people who participated in the SES session was sufficiently large to allow a meaningful conversation?						
2	PE.PR.5	Do you believe that the group of people who participated in the SES session was adequately diverse to allow various opinions to be expressed?						
3	PE.PR.8	Do you believe that the SES session's facilitation (i.e., moderator, boards, and supportive material) allowed a meaningful conversation?						
4	SE.PR.1 , SP.DS.5	Did your participation in the SES session improve your understanding of potential developments (e.g., technological, demographical and economic developments) that could affect your region by 2022 and beyond?						
5	SE.PE.2	In the future, will you more actively search for information about controversial technologies (such as self-driving cars) because you participated in the RRI2SCALE SES session?						
6	PE.O.4, SP.EP.7	Did your participation in the SES session improve your understanding of any current dilemmas in your region (e.g., the dilemma of boosting innovation and economic growth at the expense of other social and environmental objectives)?						
7	PE.PE.2	Did your participation in the SES session increase your trust in the regional authorities?						
8	E.PE.1	Do you believe that analysing potential ethical issues must be an integral part of the strategic planning of the regional authority?						
9	E.PE.2	In the future, will you search more actively information about ethically controversial research-endeavours (such as mouse experiments) because you participated in the RRI2SCALE SES session?						

10	PE.O.5	Did meeting new people in the SES session lead (or may lead in the future) to new partnerships, networks, or network coalitions?						
11	SE.PR.2	Would you describe the SES session as a good opportunity for your region to advance towards awareness of the impact of science and technology on society?						

Which is your region of residence?

- Vestland (Norway)
- Overijssel (the Netherlands)
- Kriti (Greece)
- Galicia (Spain)

You participated in this survey as a member of: (PE.PR.6)

- academia or research/ education
- governmental body / regional authority
- business
- civil society organisation
- local community
- other (please specify)

Gender: How do you identify? (GE.PR.1)

- Man
- Non-binary
- Woman
- I prefer to self describe, below:

#	Identifier	Question	Very much	Some what	Neutr al	Not really	Not at all	Undec ided
1	GE.PR.2	Do you believe that the SES session took place in a gender-equal environment?						
2	GE.PR.3	Did you observe any sexist language in the communication on the RRI2SCALE project?						
3	E.PR.1	Do you believe that the SES session complied with research integrity standards (e.g., clarity in the research goals, respect for all participants and transparency in data collection methods)?						
4	PE.PR.7	Do you believe that you had or were provided with sufficient background knowledge on the topics discussed to actively participate in the SES session?						

Q.1.1: What did you like the most about the SES session, or which aspect did you consider a weak part?

Do you participate in this survey as a member of a governmental body or a regional authority? If yes, then please reply to the following five questions. Otherwise, ignore them.

#	Identifier	Question	Very much	Some what	Neutral	Not really	Not at all	Undecided
1	SP.DS.3	Did your participation in the SES session contribute to appreciating the positions of different stakeholders?						
2	SE.PE.1 , SP.DS.4	Did your participation in the SES session contribute to perceiving new technologies as worth-investigating solutions to regional problems and challenges?						
3	SP.EP.4	Do you believe that regional policies concerning research and innovation will only enjoy social acceptance if they seriously consider ethics and social values?						

Thank you for your feedback!

Annexe 4 - Co-creation Workshop Questionnaire (M2.3)

Title: RRI2SCALE agenda-setting workshop

Description: This questionnaire aims to measure the performance and impact of the RRI2SCALE agenda-setting workshop that took place recently.

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Who we are:

We are < Insert Regional Authority Name > and we are contacting you in the framework of RRI2SCALE, a project funded by the European Union under the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation. A detailed description of how we handle personal data is presented in the Privacy Policy that accompanies this Consent Form.

Project: RRI2SCALE - Responsible Research and Innovation Ecosystems at Regional Scale for Intelligent Cities, Transport and Energy (GA Number 872526).

Partner: Organisation name: < Insert Regional Authority Name >

Address: < Insert Regional Authority Address >
 Phone: < Insert Regional Authority Phone >
 E-mail: < Insert Regional Authority Generic E-mail Address >

Responsible persons: 1. Project Manager: < Insert Name > (< Insert email >)
 2. Data Protection Officer: < Insert Name > (< Insert email >)

What do we need from you?

We need you to participate in a short survey. It won't take you more than 7 minutes. Your replies will help us to evaluate the performance and impact of the key project activities. In this context, we need to process some of your personal data:

- Some basic demographics (gender, stakeholder group);

What will we do with your data?

The project's deliverables that the survey will derive will not include your personal data or any other information that could identify you. However, we are obliged to grant access to your data to:

- EU officials such as our Project Officer for purposes related to the project's evaluation;
- EU agencies and other authorities for project auditing purposes.

How can you withdraw your consent?

You can withdraw your consent at any time by communicating by email or on the phone with the responsible persons listed above.

I hereby give my consent to the processing of my personal data needed for:

#	Consent Subject	Tick box
1	My participation in a survey that will be carried out by RRI2SCALE to evaluate the performance and impact of key project activities, such as workshops and other materials.	

Please reply to the following questions.

#		Question	Very much	Some what	Neutr al	Not really	Not at all	Undec ided
1	PE.0.3	Would you describe the discussion as a good opportunity for your region to advance towards collaborative decision-making and shared responsibility?						
2	E.O.1	Do you think policy-makers should often organise discussions like the one you just participated in to allow future policies to reflect people's needs, preferences and concerns and be aligned with social values?						
3	GO.PE.1	Do you think policy-makers should often organise discussions like the one you just participated in to not only consult citizens on their preferences but also to co-create solutions with them?						

4	E.O.3	Do you think discussions like the one you just participated in can increase citizens' trust in science and new technologies to solve regional problems?						
5	SDG.8.1	Do you think policies developed through discussions like the one you just participated in can promote economic growth and spread its fruits fairly across society?						
6	SDG.10.1	Do you think policies developed through discussions like the one you just participated in can promote the use of new technologies (such as intelligent cities, intelligent transport and intelligent energy) to reduce inequality within the region?						

Please reply to the following questions.

#		Question	Very much	Some what	Neutr al	Not really	Not at all	Undec ided
1	PE.O.2	Was the topic discussed today interesting and/or important for you?						
2	PE.O.1	Did you feel that the moderator(s) seriously considered the participants' opinions, values, and expectations to be incorporated into future agendas and/or policies?						
3	PE.PE.1	Did your participation in the discussion increase your interest in policies affecting growth, innovation and equality in your region?						
4	PE.PE.3	In the future, would you actively participate in similar discussions to co-design policies that affect growth, innovation and equality in your region?						
5	GO.PR.1	Do you think more people in your region would perceive discussions like the one you just participated in as meaningful and happily participate in the future?						
6	PE.PR.7	After all, do you believe you had sufficient background knowledge on the topics discussed to participate in the conversation actively?						

What did you like the most about the discussion, or which aspect did you consider a weak part?

You participated in this survey as a member of:

- academia or research/ education
- governmental body / regional authority
- business
- civil society organisation
- local community
- other (please specify)

Gender: How do you identify?

- Man
- Non-binary
- Woman
- I prefer to self describe, below:

Do you participate in this survey as a member of a governmental body or a regional authority? If yes, then please reply to the following two questions. Otherwise, ignore them.

#		Question	Very much	Some what	Neutr al	Not really	Not at all	Undec ided
1	SP.EP.2	Did your participation in the discussion contribute to perceiving the engagement of various stakeholders in the region’s strategic planning as a measure to democratise decision-making?						
2	SP.EP.3	In the future, would you undertake initiatives to increase public engagement in the strategic planning of your region?						

Do you participate in this survey as a member of academia or research? If yes, then please reply to the following two questions. Otherwise, ignore them.

#		Question	Very much	Some what	Neutr al	Not really	Not at all	Undec ided
1	GO.PE.2	Should universities in your region organise similar discussions to co-create with citizens the purposes or design of their research activities?						

2	PE,PE,4	In the future, would you undertake initiatives to increase public engagement in the research activities of your organisation?						
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Thank you for your feedback!

Annexe 5 - Privacy Policy

PRIVACY POLICY

LAST UPDATE: 16/11/2021

1. Who we are:

We are < Insert Regional Authority Name > and we are contacting you in the framework of RRI2SCALE, a project funded by the European Union under the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation. More information on our project can be found in project's [Web Portal](#).

CONTACT DETAILS

Organisation name: < Insert Regional Authority Name >

Phone: < Insert Regional Authority Phone >

E-mail: < Insert Regional Authority Generic E-mail Address >

Data Protection Officer: < Insert Name > (< Insert email >)

2. How we collect your personal data

We obtain personal data directly from individuals when they participate in a survey organised by us.

3. What types of data do we collect?

We only collect the data that are necessary for the smooth implementation of our project. These data fall into the following categories:

- **demographics** (gender, stakeholder group);
- **professional information** (job position);
- **information about what a person knows or believes.**

4. Bases of lawful processing

We process personal data on the following legal bases:

- Legal obligations - for processing activities required for compliance both with applicable national and European legislation as well as with the specific legal and regulatory framework of the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation of the European Union.

- Consent – for processing activities such as organisation of surveys and interviews, completing of questionnaires and dissemination of project’s results.
- Contractual obligations - for processing activities such as reporting to the European Commission and complying with project’s publicity obligations.

5. What we do with your personal data

We process your personal data with the purpose of conducting research. In particular, your replies will help us to evaluate the performance and impact of the key project activities.

6. How we secure your personal data when we process it

We continuously apply a personal data risk assessment process to identify, analyse, and evaluate the security risks that may threaten your personal data. Based on the results of this risk assessment, we define and apply a set of both technical and organisational measures to mitigate the above security risks, including but not limited to:

- Data Protection Policies to guide our personnel when processing your data;
- Written contracts with organisations that process personal data on our behalf;
- Non-Disclosure Agreements with our personnel;
- Back up process, antimalware protection, access control mechanisms, etc.
- Appointment of a Data Protection Officer.

7. Do we share personal data with third parties?

We may occasionally share personal data with trusted third parties to help us deliver efficient and quality services. When we do so, we ensure that recipients are contractually bound to safeguard the data we entrust to them before we share the data. We may engage with several or all the following categories of recipients:

- Parties that support us as we provide our services (e.g., cloud-based software services such as Dropbox, Microsoft Sharepoint, Google);
- Our professional advisers, including lawyers, auditors, and insurers;
- Dissemination services providers (e.g., MailChimp);
- Law enforcement or other government and regulatory agencies or other third parties as required by, and in accordance with applicable law or regulation;
- The European Commission according to our relevant contractual obligations.

8. Do we transfer your personal data outside the European Economic Area?

We do not own file servers located outside the European Economic Area (EEA). However, we may use cloud and / or marketing services from reputable providers such as SharePoint, DropBox, MailChimp, Google, etc., situated both inside and outside the EEA. We always check that such providers comply with the relevant GDPR requirements before start using their services.

9. Your rights

You have the following rights regarding our processing of your personal data:

- **Right to withdraw consent** – You can withdraw consent that you have previously given to one or more specified purposes to process your personal data. This will not affect the lawfulness of any processing carried out before you withdraw your consent.

- **Right of access** – You can ask us to verify whether we are processing personal data about you and, if so, to have access to a copy of such data.
- **Right to rectification and erasure** – You can ask us to correct our records if you believe they contain incorrect or incomplete information about you or ask us to erase your personal data after you withdraw your consent to processing or when we no longer need it for the purpose it was originally collected.
- **Right to restriction of processing** – You can ask us to temporarily restrict our processing of your personal data if you contest the accuracy of your personal data, prefer to restrict its use rather than having us erase it, or need us to preserve it for you to establish, exercise or defend a legal claim. A temporary restriction may apply while verifying whether we have overriding legitimate grounds to process it. You can ask us to inform you before we lift that temporary processing restriction.
- **Right to data portability** – In some circumstances, where you have provided personal data to us, you can ask us to transmit that personal data (in a structured, commonly used, and machine-readable format) directly to another entity.
- **Right to object** – You can object to our use of your personal data for direct marketing purposes, including profiling or where processing has taken the form of automated decision-making. However, we may need to keep some minimal information (e.g., e-mail address) to comply with your request to cease marketing to you.
- **Right to make a complaint to your local Data Protection Authority (DPA)** (see https://ec.europa.eu/justice/article-29/structure/data-protection-authorities/index_en.htm) regarding any concerns you may have about our data handling practices.

To ask us to do anything of the above, you can contact us by email: <Insert general email> or <Insert email of the DPO>. We will promptly examine your request against the relevant requirements of the laws and regulations governing privacy and personal data protection, and we will answer the latest within 30 days after receiving your request. We will ask you for some kind of identification (e.g. photocopy of your identity card or passport) to avoid non-authorized reveal of your personal data. If, for reasons of complexity of the request or a multitude of requests, we are unable to respond promptly, we will notify you within 30 days of any delay, which in no case may exceed two months from the expiration of the 30-day deadline.

10. How long do we retain personal data?

We retain personal data to provide our services, stay in contact with you and comply with applicable laws, regulations, and contractual obligations to which we are subject. Please note that we have an obligation to retain data concerning projects funded by the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation of the European Union for up to five years after the end of the project (unless further retention is requested by auditors). After the expiry of the retention period, and unless further legitimate grounds for retention arise, we will dispose of personal data in a secure manner.

11. Children

We do not knowingly collect, use, or disclose information from children under the age of 16. If we learn that we have collected the personal information of a child under 16 we will take steps to delete the information as soon as possible. Please immediately contact us if you become aware that a child under 16 has provided us with personal information.

12. Revisions of this Privacy Policy

This Privacy Policy is valid from 16/11/2021 and replaces any other previous notifications that we had issued in the past regarding our personal data management practices. We reserve the right to revise this Policy at any time,

and we commit to notify you of such revisions if they significantly affect your interests or fundamental rights and freedoms as a data subject.

Annexe 6 - Data Subject Request form

Data Subject Request form

This form should be used to submit a data subject request under the provisions of the European Union General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Submitter Details

Title:	
Name:	
Address:	

Type of Request

Please select the type of request you are making:

- Consent Withdrawal*
- Access request*
- Rectification of personal data*
- Erasure of personal data*
- Restriction of processing of personal data*
- Personal data portability request*
- Objection to processing of personal data*
- Request regarding automated decision making and profiling*

Personal data involved

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Request details

Request reason/justification

Name:

Signature:

Date:

Once completed, this form should be submitted via e-mail to **< Insert contact e-mail of Regional Authority >** or posted to:

< Insert Regional Authority Name >

< Insert Regional Authority Address >

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